

MANUFACTURING AND RECYCLING OF 3D PRINTED CONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLA COMPOSITES

Xiaoyong Tian, Tengfei Liu and Qingrui Wang

State Key Laboratory for Manufacturing Systems Engineering, Xi'an Jiaotong University, China

Keywords: Continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites, 3D printing, recycling, remanufacturing, PLA composites

ABSTRACT

Low-cost manufacturing and recycling technologies for high-performance continuous fiber reinforced composites are very important to industrial applications. A novel 3D printing based fabrication process of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTPCs) was proposed. Continuous carbon fiber and PLA filament were utilized as reinforcing phase and matrix, respectively, and simultaneously fed into the fused deposition modeling (FDM) process realizing the integrated preparation and forming of CFRTPCs. When the fiber content of printed composite specimens reached 27%, flexural strength of 335MPa and modulus of 30 GPa were obtained. Recycling and remanufacturing strategy for 3D printed CFRTPCs was proposed to retrieve the carbon fiber and PLA matrix in the form of PLA impregnated carbon fiber filament, which could be reused as the raw material for CFRTPCs 3D printing process. Remanufactured CFRTPCs specimens also exhibited a 25% higher bending strength than that of original ones, which experimentally demonstrated the first non-downgrade recycling process for CFRTPCs. A material recovery rate of 100% for continuous carbon fiber and 73% for PLA matrix were achieved for a better environmental impact. Energy consumption of 67.7 and 66 MJ/Kg respectively for recycling and remanufacturing processes was detected and compared with conventional methods. The proposed cleaner production pattern offered a potential strategy for the low-cost industrial application of fully recyclable composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Continuous Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites (CFRTPCs) provide design engineers with superior quality and long life span. Higher strength, lower weight, less maintenance and recycling have led to many engineering applications, which are increasingly used to replace metals in numbers of industrial, sporting and transport applications[1,2,3]. Development of new fabrication process of CFRTPCs has been attracted many research activities for many years. Processes like vacuum forming, filament winding, pultrusion, bladder-assisted molding and compression process have been used in the fabrication of CFRTPCs. In all these conventional processes complicated moulds are required and the process is expensive and time-consuming. It is difficult and even impossible to fabricate complex composite components. At the same time, CFRTPCs have not yet been properly recycled. Down cycling, such as energy or fuel recovery with little materials recovery such as reinforcement fiber was normally used in the laboratory and industrial reality. Actually, very seldom researches have been conducted on the recycling and remanufacturing of fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites. A closed loop material recycling for fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites was proposed and verified experimentally, in which a degradation recycling pattern was utilized for carbon fiber and matrix, from continuous FRTPs, long FRTPs, short FRTPs, finally to powder reinforced plastics[4,5]. A concept of direct structural recycling of thermoplastic composites was also put forward, by which that large composite products can be cut into small-size structural pieces that can be directly used to produce smaller composite products[6,7]. Nevertheless, fully recovering continuous fiber and matrix is still a challenge for the development and application of fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites[8]. Development of new and better fabrication process as well as recycling process is needed for the further development of composite materials.

Recently, some interdisciplinary researches have also been conducted to fabricate composite components by using additive manufacturing technology, also called 3D printing[9], by which the

components are fabricated by joining materials from 3D model data, usually layer upon layer as opposed to subtractive manufacturing methods. 3D printing process integrates the materials preparation process and forming process together, which provide a wide design flexibility and a reduced product development cycle. From now on, Short fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites have been prepared by fused deposition modeling and selective laser sintering processes. Halil L. Tekinalp et al.[10], Weihong Zhong et al.[11], as well as Fuda Ning et al[12] investigated short fiber reinforced acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene (ABS) composites as a feedstock for 3D-printing in terms of their processibility, microstructure and mechanical performance. Gray IV et al.[13,14] developed polypropylene (PP) strands reinforced with thermotropic liquid crystalline polymer (TLCP) fibers for FDM process and investigated the effects of FDM processing conditions on short TLCP fiber reinforced parts. According to the mentioned research activities, a limited improvement of mechanical performance, for example up to 20% of tensile strength, has been achieved by adding short fiber into the plastic feedstock due to the limitations in the reinforcement of short fiber. So, using 3D printing to fabricate CFRTPCs components with much higher performance became a cutting-edge and interdisciplinary research topic in the last few years. In 2014, Mark Forged Company developed a 3D printer for CFRTPCs process using pre-preg filament with continuous fiber and thermal plastic matrix[15]. However, how to efficiently recycle the fabricated thermoplastic composites without down-cycling was still rarely considered.

In the present research, A novel 3D printing based fabrication process of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTPCs) was proposed. Continuous carbon fiber and PLA filament were utilized as reinforcing phase and matrix, respectively, and simultaneously fed into the fused deposition modeling (FDM) process realizing the integrated preparation and forming of CFRTPCs. Process parameters, such as temperature of liquefier, layer thickness, hatch spacing, were studied and optimized according to their influence on the performance of the composites samples. At the same time, a recycling and remanufacturing process based on 3D printing process was firstly established for CFRTPCs. Then, the mechanical performance of recycled carbon filament and remanufactured CFRTPCs were systematically studied. Economical and environmental issues have been taken into considerations by analyzing the material recovery rate and energy consumption during the recycling process. Based upon these results, a new concept for cleaner production pattern of composites was conceived and discussed for the future development and application of high performance composites.

2 3D PRINTING PROCESS FOR CFRTPCS

2.1 Mechanism and equipment

A schematic representation of the 3D printing process for CFRTPCs is shown in Fig. 1a. In the process for CFRTPCs, physical parts with complex constructions are built by the deposition of an thermoplastic polymeric material with continuous fibers inside. The novel extrusion head receives the filament of thermoplastic material and heats it to a semiliquid state in the nozzle. Meanwhile, continuous fiber is fed from the fiber supply coil and goes through the inner bore of the extrusion head to the nozzle. Hence, the continuous fiber is infiltrated and coated by the molten thermoplastic polymer inside the nozzle, and the impregnated composites can be extruded out from the egress of the nozzle. When the extruded material reaches the surface of the part, it solidifies rapidly and adheres to the previous layer so that the fiber can be pulled out continually by the foregoing fiber inside the part. On the other hand, the extrusion head, which is connected to X-Y motion mechanism, can move along the cross section contour and the filling trajectory obtained from a 3D CAD system, and generate single layer of the part. After one layer is completed, the building platform placed on a lift mechanism moves in the Z axis direction by an increasement equal to the layer thickness. The process is repeated until the part is finished. The equipment for CFRTPCs was independently developed and set up based on the schematic, which consists of extrusion head, control system, building platform, X-Y motion mechanism etc.. as shown in Fig. 1b.

Fig. 1 Schematic and equipment of 3D printing for CFRTPCs , a) scheme for 3D printing of CFRTPCs ,b) the setup for the 3D printing of CFRTPCs

2.2 Process parameters and performance

Poly lactide (PLA/1.75 mm) from FLASHFORGE Corp. in China has been used as the thermoplastic material, and carbon fiber (1000 fibers in a bundle) from TENAX-J Corp. in China has been used as the reinforcement. The CFRTPCs specimens were all prepared by the aforementioned equipment for the measurement of mechanical properties.

In the conventional forming process of composites, temperature and pressure are two important parameters to the performance of produced composites. It is same for the 3D printed CFR PLA composites except that heating happened in the printing head and pressure took place in the liquefier and between platform or deposited layer and printing nozzle, from which the melt plastics came out from the printing head. Temperature of liquefier in the printing head could be simply set as an equipment parameter. However, controlling pressure is complicated and influenced by at least two parameters, layer thickness and hatch spacing. These three parameters will be discussed in this section.

Temperature is one of the critical condition for the fabrication of composites, which has significant influence on the impregnation of fiber and matrix. In 3D printing process, temperature was also important to the bonding strength between deposited lines and layers. Temperature in 3D printed CFRTPCs process is mainly influenced by the temperature of liquefier in the printing head. Flexural strength and modulus were measured for the specimens prepared with different temperature in liquefier of the printing head. The results are shown in Fig. 2. It's obvious that the flexural strength and modulus are direct proportion to the temperature until 240oC up to 155MPa and 8.6GPa, respectively.

Fig. 2 Influence of temperature in liquefier on the flexural strength and modulus of the 3D printed CFR PLA composites

In the 3D printing CFRTPCs process, pressure took place in the liquefier and between platform or deposited layer and printing nozzle, from which the melt plastics came out from the printing head. Pressure is complicated and influenced by at least two parameters, layer thickness and hatch spacing.

Layer thickness is a featured parameter for 3D printing process, which is important to the fabrication accuracy, efficiency, and mechanical properties of normal FDM components. It is even more significant to CFR PLA composite due to the possibility to changing the carbon fiber content of the fabricated specimen. More layers will integrate more carbon fibers in the printed specimen. Several values for layer thickness were chosen from 0.3 to 0.8mm to investigate its influence on the flexual strength. The flexual strength was dramatically decreased with a enlarged value of thickness. With the layer thickness of 0.3 mm, maximum flexual strength was obtain up to 240MPa. When the layer thickness was changing from 0.4 to 0.6mm, the flexual strength of composites specimens decreased slightly, and then heavily declined with layer thickness of 0.7 and 0.8mm, as shown in Fig.3.

Fig. 3 Influence of layer thickness on the flexual strength the 3D printed CFR PLA composites

Hatch spacing is the central distance between two adjacent lines. To keep contact between adjacent lines, there must be overlaps between them. When decreasing the hatch spacing from 1.8 to 0.4 mm, the average flexual strength of 3D printed composites specimens increased from 130MPa to 335MPa, and simultaneously flexual modulus was improved from 6.26 GPa to 30 GPa, as shown in Fig.4.

Fig.4 Influence of hatch spacing on the flexual strength and modulus of the 3D printed CFR PLA composites

3 RECYCLING AND REMANUFACTURING FOR 3D PRINTED CFRTPCS

3.1 Scheme of recycling and remanufacturing

A recycling and remanufacturing strategy for aforementioned 3D printing CFRTPCS process was put forward in the present paper. As shown in Fig.5a, basically it is a reverse process to the 3D

printing of CFRTPCs. A hot air gun was employed to locally remelt matrix material on the 3D printed CFRTPCs according the reverse path of the printing process, as shown in Fig 5 b). Then, the carbon fiber was pulled out gently and continuously with the movement of the hot air gun. Resolidified thermoplastic material adhered to the fiber and formed an impregnated carbon fiber filament with a relatively rough surface. To smooth the filament surface, a remolding nozzle with a diameter of 0.8mm was used to melt the thermoplastic matrix, as shown in Fig.5c. There was no obvious damage observed on the recycled carbon fiber filament due to the protection layer of thermoplastics. The obtained thermoplastic impregnated carbon fiber filament could be rolled up or directly fed back into the 3D printing process for the remanufacturing process, as show in Fig.5 d and e. Standard samples and components were remanufactured and studied by using this recycling and remanufacturing strategy in the present research.

Fig. 5 Scheme of recycling and remanufacturing of 3D printed CFRTPCs a), and key elements for each step: b) hot air gun system, c) remolding nozzle, d) recycled impregnated filament, e) remanufacturing process

3.2 Mechanical properties of re-manufactured composites

Using traditional chemical, thermal, and mechanical recycling processes, composites can only be recycled to a lower material level, and so could be mostly reused in less critical applications. Material states and mechanical properties of the recycled and reused composites are always the most important consideration when evaluating a recycling process for composites. In this section, basic mechanical properties of 3D printed composite specimens, and recycled and remanufactured CFRTPCs were investigated and compared.

Specimens were prepared by using the recycled carbon fiber impregnated filament. Two control groups of specimens, pure PLA and virginal carbon fiber reinforced PLA, were also prepared and measured. The results are shown in Fig.6. An average flexural strength of 263MPa was obtained for the remanufactured composite specimens, which led to a relatively larger (about 25%) improvement on the flexural strength over the originally printed composites specimens. Large improvement in flexural strength must be the evidence for the improvement of interfaces, especially between the fiber tow and matrix. Recycling and remanufacturing processes provided extra melting impregnation functions for a better interface, also for an obvious improvement of flexural strength. However, the modulus of remanufactured composite specimens was slightly decreased from 14.5 GPa of originally printed composites specimens to 13.3 GPa, as shown in Fig.6. It was probably due to the degradation of thermoplastic PLA matrix during the recycling and remanufacturing processes.

Fig.6 Flexural strength and modulus of pure PLA, originally printed and re-manufactured composites specimens

According to the comparison of originally printed and remanufactured CF/PLA specimens, flexural strength were obviously improved to certain extent after the recycling and remanufacturing process. No carbon fiber was damaged during this recycling process. Meanwhile, thermal treatment in the recycling process may play a vital role to improve the bonding and impregnation between fiber and matrix, and create a superior interfacial properties.

3.3 Economical and environmental considerations

Besides the mechanical performance, considerations must be taken on the economical and environmental issues. Wastes or materials recovery rate, and energy consumption for the recycling process should be discussed.

Reinforcement fiber and PLA matrix were not separately recycled in the present method. An impregnated carbon fiber filament was obtained after recycling process. The materials recovery rate can be easily calculated by the weight ratio of recycled filament to the original composite component. An overall material recovery rate of 75% has been achieved, in which continuous carbon fiber is 100% recovered and transformed into an impregnated filament without any damage on the properties of carbon fiber. 25% weight loss in the recycling process was mainly caused by the remolding process when the debonded filament went through the remolding nozzle with a diameter of 0.8mm, in which redundant PLA was blocked by the remolding nozzle. In summary, continuous carbon fiber can be fully recycled to impregnated filaments with an improved interfacial and mechanical performance. Almost all the PLA matrix can be recycled and reused, 73wt% of which was recovered in the impregnated filament together with the continuous carbon fiber, and the rest can be collected for further usage even with slight degradation in molecular weight. The excellent material recovery efficiency would make fully recyclable “green” composites possible.

In comparison with energy consumption of movement mechanisms, energy was mainly consumed in multiple heating processes. Thermal energy was utilized in both recycling and remanufacturing processes. In the recycling process, hot wind gun was used to locally heat the composite components, leading to debonding. Remolding nozzle was heated to melt the PLA adhere to the carbon fiber. A power meter has been used to detect the energy consumption. An overall energy consumption of 67.7MJ/kg has been detected in the recycling process, which was much higher than the conventional mechanical, thermal, and chemical recycling processes, and proper recycling strategy is still under investigation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Currently, carbon fiber reinforced composites have not yet been properly recycled probably due to their inherent heterogeneous nature of matrix and the reinforcement, leading to poor materials recyclability, in particular the thermoset composites. Design and manufacturing processes are usually

conducted only for a light weight and higher mechanical performance, without any consideration of end of life (EOL) treatment. For the future composites design and manufacturing, the use of thermoplastics might be much more preferable than non-remeltable thermoset matrix. And more easily recyclable composites are strongly needed. Thus, innovative concept is required for future development in order to meet simultaneously the end-use properties and the recyclability, which are normally in contradictory with each other[3].

Recycling strategy is always linked with the material types and manufacturing process. Based on the recycling and remanufacturing process of 3D printed CFRTPCs, a cleaner production pattern of composites for the future can be conceived as shown in Fig. 7. A biodegradable thermoplastics PLA is used for the matrix of composites, which can be made from renewable materials like corn by photosynthesis functions. 3D printing process is utilized to produce a CFR PLA composites. 3D printing process itself is a clean manufacturing method without any waste of raw material and harmful emission. The performance of 3D printed composite components is considerable according to the achieved experimental results. Moreover, the printing trajectory could be reversely used for the recycling process which is a big advantage compared to other processes. After usage of printed composite components, a recycling process can be employed to transfer EOL composites to intermediate products, the impregnated carbon fiber filament, which can be directly used for the following remanufacturing process. As exhibited in the present paper, a better mechanical performance has been obtained due to the recycling process. For the first time, this results show a non-downgrade recycling process for the composite. The more interesting point is that the remanufactured composite components may experience more recycling and remanufacturing cycles. The times of these cycles could be determined by the aging of PLA matrix, which still can be optimized or compensated by refilling new PLA materials into the remanufacturing process. In this overall process, continuous carbon fiber is fully recycled and reused without any damage and degradation due to the protection of PLA matrix. The requirement for the virgin carbon fiber would be significantly reduced. Further more, real green composites will be produced in the future when high performance natural fibers like flax are used by 3D printing process. This innovative concept includes all the aspects of how to avoid environmental impact of composites, reducing the expensive raw material-carbon fiber, using renewable materials, fully recycling of composites to an up level, and remanufacturing with a higher performance. This four “Re”s production pattern for CFRTPCs is a so prefect concept for future composites that efforts must be made to realize the real industrial application.

Fig7 A four-“Re”s cleaner production pattern for CFRTPCs

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (NO. 51575430), the State Key Laboratory of Robotics and Systems - HIT (SKLRS-2015-ZD-02), the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities, XJTU, and the research funds from School of Mechanical Engineering, State Key Laboratory of Manufacturing Systems Engineering, XJTU.

REFERENCES

- [1] Qianqian Chen, Philippe Boisse, Chung Hae Park, Abdelghani Saouab, Joël Bréard. Intra/interply shear behaviors of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites in thermoforming processes. *Composite Structures* ,93 ,2011,pp.1692–1703.
- [2] Stewart, R., Thermoplastic composites — recyclable and fast to process. *Reinforced Plastics* 55,2011,pp. 22-28.
- [3] Yang, Y., Boom, R., Irion, B., van Heerden, D., Kuiper, P., de Wit, H., Recycling of composite materials. *Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification* 51, 2012, pp.53-68.
- [4] Colucci, G., Ostrovskaya, O., Frache, A., Martorana, B., Badini, C., 2015, The effect of mechanical recycling on the microstructure and properties of PA66 composites reinforced with carbon fibers. *J APPL POLYM SCI* 132.
- [5] Kemmochi, K., Takayanagi, H., Nagasawa, C., Takahashi, J., Hayashi, R., 1995, Possibility of closed loop material recycling for fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites. *ADVANCED PERFORMANCE MATERIALS* 2, 385-394.
- [6] Asmatulu, E., Twomey, J., Overcash, M., 2014, Recycling of fiber-reinforced composites and direct structural composite recycling concept. *J COMPOS MATER* 48, 593-608.
- [7] Schinner, G., B., J., H., A., 1996. Recycling carbon-fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites. *J. Thermoplast. Compos.* 9, 239.
- [8] Oliveux, G., Dandy, L.O., Leeke, G.A., 2015, Current status of recycling of fibre reinforced polymers: Review of technologies, reuse and resulting properties. *PROG MATER SCI* 72, 61-99.
- [9] Wohlers, T., 2015, Wohlers Report 2015 - 3D Printing and Additive Manufacturing State of the Industry Annual World Worldwide Progress Report, WOHLERS ASSOCIATES, INC.
- [10] Halil L. Tekinalp, Vlastimil Kunc, Gregorio M. Velez-Garcia, Chad E. Duty, Lonnie J. Love, Amit K. Naskar, Craig A. Blue, Soydan Ozcan. Highly oriented carbon fiber – polymer composites via additive manufacturing. *Composites Science and Technology* 105 (2014) 144–150.
- [11] Weihong Zhong, Fan Li, Zuoguang Zhang, Lulu Song, Zhimin Li. Short fiber reinforced composites for fused deposition modeling. *Materials Science and Engineering A* 301 (2001) 125–130.
- [12] Fuda Ning, Weilong Cong, Jingjing Qiu, Junhua Wei, Shiren Wang. Additive manufacturing of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites using fused deposition modeling. *Composites Part B* 80(2015)369-378.
- [13] Gray IV RW, Baird DG, Bohn JH. Thermoplastic composites reinforced with long fiber thermotropic liquid crystalline polymers for fused deposition modeling. *Polym Compos* 1998;19(4):383–94.
- [14] Robert W. Gray IV, Donald G. Baird, Jan Helge Bøhn. Effects of processing conditions on short TLCP fiber reinforced FDM parts. *Rapid Prototyping Journal*. Volume 4 Number 1 1998 14–25.
- [15] Makeforged company, US, <http://markforged.com/>.